

HISTORY OF DEVELOPMENT OF INTERNATIONAL LAW

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Abstract: definition of the concept of "international law" is one of the most important tasks of the science of international law. If, state and law if the science of theory studies the phenomena characteristic of the national legal system of states, and the science of international law is specific to interstate or international relations in a broader sense examines the legal features of events and processes. This is it the article describes the history of the development of international law in detail.

Key words: international, law, historical development, socio-legal practice.

The concept of international law means public international law. Legally regulates the legal relations of states (subjects) participating in and participating in international public law. International public law determines the basic international principles of international relations between states. International public law represents inter-state national relations, states and people's governments, the basic rights, duties and freedoms of citizens on an international scale, international law and other relations related to the resolution of international disputes and disagreements. International law is a set of public legal principles and norms that regulate relations between states and other participants (subjects) in international communication. In contrast to the domestic law of the state, the object of international law is international, or more precisely, interstate relations, which go beyond the competence of a separate state in terms of its content. Unlike domestic law, there are no legislative bodies responsible for creating and enforcing international law. States are the main subjects of international law. The norms of international law created by their mutual agreement express the agreed will of the states. This is the peculiarity of international law. Various international treaties, agreements, agreements, conventions, declarations, UN documents are the normative basis of international law.

International law is the regulation of friendly and diplomatic relations between states is a separate legal system consisting of principles and norms. From this In addition, several definitions of international law are given, their general concept can be expressed as follows: International law is to ensure peace and cooperation is a system of legal norms regulating interstate relations. International law is very broad and includes various branches of special rights is a system. The main features of the law characteristic of all national legal systems is also characteristic of international law. It has the character of a state office and is a certain social one consists of a system of legal norms regulating relations. This compliance with norms is provided by state obligation in necessary cases. Internal state subjects consist of individuals, legal entities and state bodies. International and subjects of law are basically

sovereign over whom there is no rule from countries, international and interstate organizations, fighting for independence consists of growing nations and peoples. International law has its own subject of action. These interstate relations, in general, all of the international legal system relations between subjects. Norms of international law are its subjects is created through transactions made by International as well as domestic law and by the state to ensure compliance with international norms provides for the use of the method of coercion.

Modern international law is divided into international public law and international private law. International public law legally regulates the relations of states and other subjects participating in international relations. Private international law regulates property and other relations between citizens and organizations of different countries, their legal status, jurisdiction, and the procedure and conditions for applying the national legislation of the country where they live. Public international law includes areas such as international treaty law, diplomatic and consular law, international organizations law, international human rights law, international economic law, international environmental law, international criminal law, international maritime law, international air law, international space law. . There are generally recognized principles of international law. They are universally binding norms that are of great importance in the implementation of international law. Most of the principles of international law are stated in Article 2 of the UN Charter. They are in accordance with the UN Charter, 1970 on Principles of International Law Relating to Friendly Relations and Cooperation among States. It is explained in detail in the Declaration and the Final document of the Security and Cooperation

The origin of international law is a natural objective process. The general condition for the emergence of international law is the will of states not the conditions of human life, its historical development, human surroundings interaction with the world, social division of labor, emergence of states being and developing. International law is an important legal category, from international relations, grew out of their economic, political, military, cultural and other characteristics. Thus, the emergence of international law is directly related to the existence of states related to its arrival and development. Objective conditions of development of states establishing political, economic, cultural and legal relations between them causes the necessity. The result is an independent system of law as the emergence and development of international law. The current era is international international organizations for the right, environmental protection as a new international is characterized by the emergence of legal fields.

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